

A SIMPLE WISDOM TOOTH EXTRACTION

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Abstract: It was found that 20% of healthy people have a pathology associated with eruption of wisdom teeth. Infectious and inflammatory processes developing during this period are especially dangerous. They tend to spread to the soft tissues of the maxillofacial region, neck, as well as to penetrate with blood flow into the brain.

Keywords: wisdom tooth, retention, surgical dentistry

Introduction. The third molar is more often called the wisdom tooth or the "eight" (the third molar is the 8th from the middle of the dentition). It is not preceded by a baby tooth, and the eruption does not occur in the prenatal period, but at the age of 3 to 5 years. The "eight" erupts later than others, when the jaw bones completely or partially stopped growing at the age of 14 to 30 years, sometimes even later. Growth and eruption are completely dependent on the hereditary characteristics of the body.

The crown of the third molar looks no different from the crowns located next to it. The main features are in the structure of the roots and root canals. As a rule, there are several channels. They are meandering, narrow and not always located in a separate root. 2-3 roots are considered the norm, but sometimes there are more, fewer or just one root, and several channels can be seen in it. This makes it very difficult to treat caries.

Normally erupted, performing all its functions, the third molar does not need to be removed. Even caries of the eight can be cured quite successfully. In the future, it can become a support for a non-removable prosthesis. If the wisdom tooth hurts, removal occurs only according to indications and after an examination. Indications for removal are, first of all, pain and discomfort that occur in the patient during eruption. With these symptoms, he goes to the dentist, and he already decides what exactly needs to be done after an examination and radiography. The "Eight" is removed if available:

1. deep caries, which cannot be treated for some reason, mainly due to the inaccessibility or obstruction of root canals (they are often narrow, tortuous);
2. pericoronitis (pericoronitis)- inflammation of the gum (hood) covering the erupting molar from above;

3. retention – the "eight" cannot break through the bone tissue, which leads to the development of infectious and inflammatory processes in the soft tissues and bone tissue of the jaw;

4. dystopia – growth is directed not vertically, but to the side, which leads to injury to the surrounding tissues, malocclusion and growth of the remaining teeth in the dentition due to the lack of the necessary place for this (the second molar may be especially affected);

5. the need to install braces in case of improper growth or crowding of teeth in the dentition – third molars can disrupt this process;

6. infringement of the branches of the trigeminal nerve, accompanied by attacks of severe pain or discomfort (paresthesia).

Sometimes the incorrect growth of the third molar is detected even before the patient complains. In such cases, the dentist also recommends its removal.

The growth and eruption of the third molar is often accompanied by infectious and inflammatory processes of the surrounding soft tissues. This is due to the fact that the "eight" often begins to erupt under the hood – the gum covering it. An infection penetrates under the hood and an inflammatory process develops. The course can be acute or chronic, inflammation can be catarrhal, purulent or ulcerative. Symptoms of pericoronitis:

- unpleasant sensations in the eruption area – discomfort, itching, pain;
- putrid breath;
- swelling of tissues, pain when chewing, sometimes convulsive jaw spasm (trism);
- increased body temperature (not always);
- enlargement and soreness of the submandibular and cervical lymph nodes.

Conclusions: If you suspect improper eruption and inflammation of the gums, it is better to immediately consult a dentist, without waiting for serious complications. Depending on the pathology, the dentist may prescribe therapeutic treatment, remove the hood or tooth.

The third molar is removed strictly according to indications. An experienced doctor will perform the operation absolutely painlessly. If this is a simple deletion, then it will only take a few minutes. With a complex operation, it will be longer (depending on the problem), but also painless. Professionalism is required from the doctor in this situation, and a positive attitude and calmness are required from the patient.

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References:

1. Arsenina O.I. Early orthodontic and orthopedic measures in the complex treatment of patients with defects and deformities of the mandible. Diss. ... MD - M.2018. - 412s.;
2. Betelman A.I., Pozdnyakova A.I., Mukhina A.D., Alexandrova Yu.M. Orthopedic dentistry for children. — Kiev, "Zdorov'ya"., 1965.-408 p.; Ham A.W. Histology. Second edition. Philadelphia-London-Monreal. 2018. 864 p. ;
3. Betelman A.I., Pozdnyakova A.I., Mukhina A.D., Alexandrova Yu.M. Orthopedic dentistry for children. — Kiev, "Zdorov'ya"., 2019.-408 p.;
4. Betelman A.I., Pozdnyakova A.I., Mukhina A.D., Alexandrova Yu.M. Orthopedic dentistry for children. — Kiev, "Zdorov'ya"., 2015.-408 p.;

